

EU MAP webinar : European Quality schemes: the added value for mountain value chains

Highlights Report

8 November 2022

The second **MOVING** (MOuntain Valorisation through INterconnectedness and Green growth) **EU Multi-Actor Platform webinar** on Mountain Value Chains: heterogeneity and innovation took place on 8 November 2022.

The main objectives of this webinar were:

- Present the MOVING project and publicise the **EU-MAP**;
- Provide an update of the new the European Commission legislative proposal on EU Quality schemes
- Discuss about the implementation and added value of the EU quality schemes and the implications for mountain value chains;

The webinar started with two presentations on the progress made by MOVING and the results achieved during the first two years of the project, as well as its **Community of Practice** (CoP).

The focus of the event was the revision of the EU quality policy. The representative of the European Commission introduced the novelties its proposal will bring for producers and also its implications for mountain value chains. Our partners from the Association of European Regions for Products of Origin (AREPO) presented their position and some policy recommendations on **the revision of the EU Geographical Indications System (GIs)**, which does not define sustainability. In addition, the implementation of the EU optional quality term “mountain product” and its benefits were also tackled.

The event featured other presentations of four **reference regions** of the project, which showed the implications of the quality scheme to the different mountain value chains: (i) Serra da Estrela PDO Cheese value chain (Cordilheira Central); (ii) Alto-Molise Dairy value chain (Central Apennines), (iii) Trento PDO Wine value chain (Eastern Alps), and (iv) Sjenica lamb PDO value chain (Dinaric Mountains).

The webinar concluded with a round table discussion with representatives from University of Cordoba (Spain), University of Evora (Portugal), University of Molise (Italy), VINIDEA, (Italy), AREPO (Belgium), MENA Group (Serbia), Euromontana, European Commission (DG AGRI) and AEIDL (Belgium). They discussed the main challenges and opportunities in mountain areas face to introduce EU quality schemes.

ORGANISER:

 8 NOVEMBER 2022

 ONLINE

 62 PARTICIPANTS
(research, public authorities, advisors, business, producers, other EU-funded projects, etc.)

 15 COUNTRIES

 PRESENTATIONS AND RECORDINGS [HERE](#)

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GETTING TO KNOW MOVING

MOVING: first year of progress and results

María del Mar DELGADO

MOVING Coordinator, University of Cordoba

Mar Delgado from the University of Cordoba (Spain), the coordinator of MOVING, presented the progress made and the results achieved during the first two years of the project.

Funded by the Horizon 2020 programme, MOVING is a four-year project (2020-2024) gathering 23 partner organisations. It aims to build capacities and co-develop relevant policy frameworks across Europe for the establishment of value chains (VCs) that contribute to the resilience and sustainability of mountain areas to climate change and other threats, such as depopulation.

The project is structured to study **23 Mountain Reference Regions** from 16 EU Member States and neighbouring countries. MOVING is carrying out a characterisation study to allow the establishment of linkages between the land use system specific to each of these regions and major changes in large-scale environmental conditions that can be foreseen. MOVING is also addressing the transferability of this place-based research to understanding change processes in similar areas.

In relation to the main outputs that MOVING has achieved so far, Professor Delgado highlighted **the inventory of 453 value chains** from across Europe's mountain areas, and the MOVING **Conceptual**

and Analytical Framework (CAF), which will be refined in the next period. The project has also created a vulnerability conceptual framework to analyse how the natural resources that support each of the value chains in MOVING's mountain areas are affected by different threats and are vulnerable to different drivers.

Initiating its third year, MOVING is finishing the value chain analysis, which is divided into three levels: the analysis of a value chain in each region, the analysis interaction of each VC with its Social-Ecological System, and the upscaling to understand what we know about the wider mountain regions that the project is working with. In addition, MOVING partners have been organising **youth engagement workshops** in order to understand how young people see the future in mountain areas and their needs to stay there.

The next step of the project is to finalise the MOVING app, develop some visual tools, and create 23 digital stories describing each of MOVING's value chains. The comparative assessment of value chains, and a foresight analysis with a scenario to 2050, are also on the to-do list of the project. All the activities carried out during the remainder months of the project will be used to develop key policy recommendations and a roadmap.

MOVING: Community of Practice and the EU Multi-Actor Platform

Miranda GARCÍA

Communication officer of MOVING, AEIDL

Miranda García from AEIDL presented and gave some updates on the MOVING **Community of Practice** (CoP), which is a core feature of the project. It is understood as a European-wide ScienceSociety-Policy interface to engage different stakeholders around resilience to climate change of mountain value chains.

In practice, the CoP is built upon 23 regional Multi-Actor Platforms (MAPs), established in the 23 Reference Regions, one European-level Multi-Actor Platform (EU MAP), and external actors. In these two years of the project, nearly 820 had joined the community.

Part of this MOVING CoP is the EU MAP, an open space for stakeholders that are interested to exchange, learn and interact at the EU level to: (a) contribute to key MOVING deliverables, and (b) support peer-to-peer exchanges on additional topics relevant to the members and for the regional MAPs.

Among the different activities that have taken place during these years, she mentioned MOVING's contribution to four open

consultations: (a) the **EU Roadmap for sustainable carbon cycles**, (b) the Mountain Education and Innovation Manifesto (**MEIM**), (c) the **brain drain**, and (d) the **sustainable EU food system**.

In addition, a virtual platform for the EU MAP members was launched in November 2021, two webinars had been organised, a briefing about MOVING's **contribution to the Long-Term Vision for Rural Areas** (LTVRA) had been published, and an **article** and infographic had been produced in collaboration with Mountain Partnership (FAO) for the International Mountain Day 2021.

Meet, share, exchange and learn from relevant European players. Join the EU MAP by expressing your interest [here](#).

RELATED WORK FROM EXTERNAL PARTERS

Session Facilitated by Serafin Pazos-Vidal, Senior Expert, Rural and Territorial Development (AEIDL)

New EU quality policy and the implications to mountain value chains

Branka TOME
DG AGRI - Unit F.3 Geographical Indications, European Commission

Branka Tome, the Deputy Head of Unit responsible for geographical indications (DG AGRI) provided a general overview of the new European quality policy, currently a hot topic among stakeholders and in the European institutions. The Commission believes that this proposal will provide better protection for geographical indications (GIs) in order to empower producers.

The main objectives of the legislative proposal is to (a) strengthen the EU system of GIs, (b) increase GIs' uptake across the Union, and (c) shorten the registration time of the new protected names.

There was also some debate around the "mountain product" label. Ms Tome explained that "despite being part of the quality schemes legislation, there are no changes proposed in that area because mountain product labels are rather new". She mentioned that the main rules are from 2012 and the details rules from 2014, so Member States needed some time to implement them in order to have the possibility to label the mountain products with the correspondent label.

With the revision of the GIs system, the Commission wants to harmonise the rules across sectors to protect the specificities of the spirit drinks sector or agriculture products, for instance. In

practice, these common provisions will allow the same procedure for registration of a name, amendment and cancellation among all sectors, except for the wine. Due to its specificity, the control of the wine will remain the same as now.

Furthermore, the new regulation will bring some novelties for producers such as (a) a wider scope covering all agricultural products, (b) the voluntary addition of sustainability requirements in the product specification, (c) the designation of a recognised producer group, a GI certificate or the continuous collaboration of the European Union Intellectual Property Office (EUIPO) to shorten applications' scrutiny times.

The Traditional Specialities Guaranteed (TSGs) has also a mention in the new EU quality policy. This scheme has not been very used after 30 years of existence due to its complexity. According to Ms Tome, there are only 89 TSGs compared to 3500 GIs. In order to increase its uptake, the scheme will be clarified and simplified.

In November 2023, the new EU quality policy will be voted on by the European Parliament, a key step towards this proposal eventual approval.

AREPO's position and policy recommendations on the EC proposal on the revision of EU GIs

Francesca ALAMPI and Giulia SCAGLIONI
AREPO

Giulia Scaglioni and Francesca Alampi, MOVING partners representing the the Association of European Regions for Products of Origin (AREPO), presented their position and some policy recommendations on the European Commission's proposal on the [revision of the EU Geographical Indications System](#) (GIs).

They consider that the proposal does not define sustainability, sustainability undertakings nor sustainability standards. The AREPO representatives fear that this can lead to a lack of a holistic approach, and it has a risk of standardisation by not considering the territorial dimension and specificities.

AREPO also pointed out the need for public financial support because most producers are not aware of GI contribution to sustainability or lack the capacity to integrate all sustainability elements into the management of their GI system. For this reason, our MOVING partner recommended the following actions to protect producers in front of this new regulation:

- Clearly detail the division of competencies;
- Clarify that the registration procedures remain strictly free of charge;
- Introduce training for GIs producers and producer groups;

- Avoid the double system of governance to assure balance representativeness;
- Consider national specificities.

In addition, Ms Alampi and Ms Scaglioni stressed that the European Commission should maintain the responsibility and the competencies over registration, amendment, cancellation and opposition procedures, and not EUIPO. However, the expertise of this institution could be useful and enriching on Intellectual Property Rights and administrative issues.

The representatives of AREPO also highlighted the main socio-economic benefits of GIs. According to them, they are not a magical tool, but they contribute to strengthening rural areas and creating job opportunities that are consolidated over time, even in companies with low productivity. But in the production characteristics is the sustainability of these companies: consumers' willingness to pay and a higher market price.

They also mentioned the existing initiatives to assess and monitor the contributions of GIs to sustainability, such as the [FAO guide](#), the Strength2food project and the Qualimentaire organisation.

RELATED WORK FROM EXTERNAL PARTERS

Session Facilitated by Serafin Pazos-Vidal, Senior Expert, Rural and Territorial Development (AEIDL)

Implementation of the EU optional quality term “mountain product”

Guillaume CORRADINO
Director of Euromontana

The director of **Euromontana**, Guillaume Corradino, shared insights on the implementation of the EU optional quality term (OQT) –a tool that helps farmers to market products made in difficult natural conditions– for “mountain products”.

There is existing legislation that considers as a mountain product both the raw materials and the feedstuffs for farm animals that come essentially from mountain areas. In the case of processed products, it is only considered a mountain product if the processing also takes place in mountain areas.

In practice, it is up to the Member States to implement this, therefore, each country has to define (a) the area for allowing or derogating the processing, (b) the conditions for the controls, (c) the use of the logo, (d) the need of authorisations or notifications from farmers, and (e) the use of a database to keep track of the use of this quality term.

Even if it is not used in all Member States, Mr Corradino highlighted the main benefits this optional quality label can bring to the territory. It enables farmers to market the product better but also

ensures certain characteristics are clear to the consumer, prevents fraudulent use of “mountain product” with clear, simple legislation (the only criteria is geography), and becomes an alternative for producers who cannot access other quality schemes.

Romania, Italy, France and Germany were the countries cited by the director of Euromontana to visualise the different levels of implementation of the EU OQT, ranging from the maximalist approach in Romania to the minimalist approach of Germany.

The revision of the EU quality schemes doesn't affect the OQT, something really positive according to Mr Corradino. He sees it essential to better understand the actual impact of this tool on farmers and local economies, and also if it overlaps or complements other quality schemes.

Find out more about the implementation of the EU optional quality term with **Euromontana's study** on the topic.

GETTING TO KNOW MOVING's VALUE CHAINS

Session Facilitated by Serafin Pazos-Vidal, Senior Expert, Rural and Territorial Development (AEIDL)

Serra da Estrela PDO Cheese value chain

Catarina ESGALHADO
University of Évora

Catarina Esgalhado from the [University of Evora](#) presented the work being carried out in [Cordilheira central Reference Region](#) on the Serra da Estrela protected designation of origin (PDO) cheese value chain.

The region, located in the centre of the Iberian Peninsula, extends longitudinally between Portugal and Spain for 700 km long. Due to its mass and altitude, Estrela is the most important mountain area in mainland Portugal (1993 m). The delimited Reference Region, influenced by 3 types of climate -Atlantic, Mediterranean and Continental-, has the status of a natural park and also of a GeoPark.

She explained the selected value chain and the characteristics and criteria of the VC quality scheme. Known as one of the most expensive cheeses in Portugal, Serra da Estrela is an artisanal product certified since 1996. It is developed from traditional knowledge of cheese manufacture techniques, using only milk from two autochthonous sheep breeds, thistle flower and salt. It used to be sold in 1 kg but after a revision of its specifications, it started to be sold also in ½ kg.

Among the main actions to improve the resilience and sustainability of the value chain and the territory, Ms Esgalhado pointed out the need to invest in marketing in order to have a uniform branding strategy, which would benefit this cheese's internationalisation.

Developing other products related to the value chain such as lamb and wool will be essential, as well as the creation of incentives for high-altitude grazing. This will require the articulation of different entities to capitalise on shepherding as shrub control. This latter action is crucial because, according to her, this was the area that burned the most last year (26.000 hectares) due to the lack of control.

Find out more about the Cordilheira central Reference Region, its selected value chain and the regional multi-actor platform (MAP), [here](#).

Alto-Molise Dairy value chain

Raiza ROCHA
University of Molise

Raiza Rocha from the [University of Molise](#) provided a presentation about the work being carried out in the [Central Apennines Reference Region](#) (Italy) on the Alto-Molise dairy value chain.

She provided information on the location of the region and more specifically on the Mountain Reference Landscape (MRL) as well as its area, and average income. This region is characterised by extensive pastures and wooded areas dedicated to livestock farming (cheese and meat) and forestry-related products..

Among all these products, cheesemaking is the most popular activity due to its contribution to the area. Using the raw milk from local breeders as the main ingredient, this value chain establishes a sustainable connection between the landscape and the production of dairy goods within a specific culture such as transhuman mountain farming and artisan culture.

Despite the current scenario marked by rural depopulation and agricultural abandonment, Ms Rocha explained that the main local actors have managed to innovate the traditional production in order to promote the region. This allows to (a) valorise the natural resources conservation, (b) refresh the cultural traditional heritage, (c) revitalise rural areas and (d) promote the assemblage with other value chains such as meat and tourism.

In addition, she indicated the challenges of resilience that Alto-Molise Dairy value chain faces. According to her, internal conflicts of the value chain between traditional and new producers, new breeding techniques, climate change factors and the consequences of war and energy crisis are the main barriers.

Finally, regarding future perspectives to improve the resilience and sustainability of the value chain and the territory, she concluded:

- Possibility of reinforcing milk and meat farming methods
- Pricing milk based on quality of pastures
- Improve logistics and distribution systems
- Foster tourism
- Mobilise resources to engage young people to the territory
- Marketing strategies to increase consumer awareness of the environmental and social benefits

Find out more about the Central Apennines Reference Region, its selected value chain and the regional multi-actor platform (MAP), [here](#).

GETTING TO KNOW MOVING's VALUE CHAINS

Session Facilitated by Serafin Pazos-Vidal, Senior Expert, Rural and Territorial Development (AEIDL)

Trento PDO Wine value chain

Ekaterina KLESHCHEVA
VINIDEA

Ekaterina Kleshcheva from [VINIDEA](#) presented the work being carried out in [Eastern Alps Reference Region](#) (Italy) on the Trento Protected Designation of Origin (PDO) wine value chain.

She briefly introduced the territory, emphasising the main agricultural activities, which are (a) the extensive cattle production on pasture, mainly for milk production and PDO quality cheese, (b) fruit production, especially apples, but also some berries, and (c) grapevine for several PDO wines.

The Trento DOC wine is an historical and well-established value chain characterised by a diversity of business models. The “mountain” origin seems to be one of the key values of this product according to Ms Kleshcheva.

The PDO standards of Trento DOC have been certified since 1993 and guarantee (a) professionalism in cultivating grapevines and attentive selection of grapes, (b) grapes' origin, (c) varieties used, (d) inclusion of other wine-making process in the bottle, and (e) ong

ageing on the lees. However, there is still no specific linkage to the mountain origin of the product and the standards do not include environmental and/or social sustainability characterisation.

Lastly, she mentioned the next steps to improve the resilience and sustainability of the Trento DOC wine value chain. It is essential to connect quality schemes to marketing strategy in order to enhance credibility and increase added value of mountain origin products. Increasing rural vitality by attracting young professionals to the sector is also necessary as well as the introduction of environmental sustainability standards.

Find out more about the Eastern Alps Reference Region, its selected value chain and the regional multi-actor platform (MAP), [here](#).

Find out more about the Eastern Alps Reference Region, its selected value chain and the regional multi-actor platform (MAP), [here](#).

Sjenica lamb PDO value chain

Tamara ZIVADINOVIC
MENA Group

Tamara Zivadinovic from MENA Group provided a presentation about the work being carried out in [Dinaric Mountains Reference Region](#) (Serbia) on the Sjenica lamb Protected Designation of Origin (PDO) value chain. This is a local product that was registered in 2012 at the Serbian national level and not at EU level.

She described the territory in which MOVING is carrying out its activities: the region of Sjenica/Pester Plateau. It is a protected area with several natural reserves as well as many endangered and protected species. The predominant economic activity in this multicultural rural area is agriculture, with an emphasis on livestock production (cattle and sheep).

In addition, Ms Zivanovic provided an overview of the characteristics and criteria of the Sjenica lamb PDO value chain. Based on a free range livestock system, there is traditional knowledge of local farmers that has been passed down from generation to generation, becoming a family production.

This PDO is characterised by (a) the specific breed of the Sjenica sheep, which is very particular due to its adaptation to harsh

conditions, and (b) the dependency on middlemen because of the lack of connection between producers and cooperatives and associations.

The region of Sjenica lamb production is famous not only for the lamb but also for other two PDOs such as Sjenica cheese (in brine) and dry sheep meat (stelja).

Finally, she spoke about the actions to improve resilience and sustainability in relation to:

- Internationalisation of the PDO
- Availability of specific cuts in shops and restaurants
- Innovative ways in production, processing and product promotion
- Adaptation to new environment conditions

You can find out more about the Dinaric Mountains Reference Region, its selected value chain and the regional multi-actor platform (MAP), [here](#).

ROUND TABLE

European Quality schemes: the added value for mountain value chains

Mar Delgado from University of Córdoba, Branka Tome from DG AGRI, Guillaume Corradino from Euromontana, Francesca Alampi and Giulia Scaglioni from AREPO, Catarina Esgalhado from University of Évora, Raiza Rocha from University of Molise, Ekaterina Kleshcheva from VINIDEA, Tamara Zivadinovic from MENA Group and Serafín Pazos-Vidal from AEIDL.

Mountain areas face different social, economic and environmental challenges to innovation and improving their resilience and sustainability. During the round table, various topics were discussed and seminar participants were given space to intervene.

Key take-home messages include:

- Quality schemes have a great potential to significantly contribute to mountain economies. They are really important to boost the gastronomic and cultural identity of a given mountain area, while ensuring the survivability of mountain food production systems and local employment. It is a way of differentiation and a guarantee that there are special features that are linked to a product.
- Quality schemes should be a value, not a burden for producers and for the actors participating in the mountain value chains. For this reason, a strong collective governance is needed that can also help producers understand the added value of complying with Quality scheme regulations. European and national institutions have to be able to stimulate producers, and once they have registered a product, avoid their misuse.
- Simplicity in the registration process is key. Producers apply for the easiest and the most flexible schemes and not the ones

that are overly complicated or require too many controls and steps.

- The investment and engagement of the farmers with these quality schemes will have an impact on the consumers' perception. That is why these two issues should not be addressed separately. In addition, networking and events like this second MOVING EU MAP webinar can contribute a lot to raise awareness about the benefits of geographical indications: traditions, specialties, guarantees, and the products that are produced in mountain areas.
- In the case of wine, this product is very regulated at the European level. However, the revision of the PDO regulation and the introduction of the sustainability concept could be a challenge in the near future. Even though some producers are introducing some sustainability practices on different levels by their own will, it may be difficult to have common approval. It would not be easy to find at the consortium level a common understanding of sustainability and most of all, the economic efforts that any of them is actually ready to put into these modifications.

Do you want to know more about the project and the community? Find more information, [here](#).
Join the EU MAP by expressing your interest, [here](#).
Or sign up for the newsletter, [here](#).

ANNEX

Internal session of EU MAP members

Taking advantage of the webinar, MOVING organised an internal session for all the EU MAP members to take stock of what has been done during these years. Miranda García from AEIDL, the EU MAP coordinator, summarised the activities carried out by this platform, which were mentioned before during her intervention.

In addition, she gave a brief update of the stakeholders who have joined the EU MAP. Until June 2022, the total number of members of the EU MAP was 48, of which 54% were women and 46% were men. Nowadays, in November 2022, there are nearly 60. Although gender representation is balanced, there is a strong representation of researchers, but there are also other type of stakeholders such as NGOs, policy authorities, and people from EU funded projects.

Besides, participants were divided into two breakout rooms to discuss how the MOVING Community of Practice and the EU MAP can contribute to the new knowledge needs. After the exchange of ideas and perspectives, these were the main conclusions of the discussions:

Key take-home messages include:

- Need clear messages and objectives about the EU MAP, and also a clarification about the registration process. This should be done by providing guidance for new participants.
- Promote new opportunities and in person meetings in order to share common interests between actors in the same region
- Further discussions are needed on key topics such as how to engage young people because they are not motivated to stay in mountain regions and this leads to a lack of legacy between older and young generations.
- The use of English is a limiting factor for the engagement of some local stakeholders, and also the use of scientific language. In order to avoid barriers, it is recommended to translate the work carried out and use non-technical language.
- There is a lack of motivation to join the EU MAP because the platform is not suited for everyone. For this reason, new ways to approach stakeholders should be considered.
- Provide more impactful and interactive sessions to foster the knowledge exchange.

From MOVING we should spread the role of advisors, very important for the producers.

What are the next steps of the EU MAP?

Over the next two years, more webinars focused on a specific topic will be organised. In August 2021, and in May and June 2022 we carried out a survey about ideas and expectations for the EU MAP and respondents indicated their thematic preference for the upcoming EU MAP activities.

Among others, these are the topics EU MAP members are keener on to address: (a) innovation in governance systems in mountain areas, (b) engaging youth of mountain areas in the LTVRA, (c) women move mountains (aligned with the International Mountain Day 2022), (d) Mountain Value Chains: heterogeneity and innovation (a second event presenting other MOVING value chains), and (e) impact of the agri-environmental measures of the CAP in mountain areas.

MOVING has also prepared a briefing on the Reference Region and Natural Sites, which will be published at the beginning of the next year. The project is also in contact with UNESCO, specifically with the World Network of Mountain Biosphere Reserves, the people who relaunched this global network, for a future event that will take place after the publication of this briefing.